

Behavioral activation for depression:
Protocol for a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Introduction

Various psychotherapies have been found to be effective in treating adult depression, including cognitive behavior therapy, interpersonal psychotherapy, problem-solving therapy, brief psychodynamic therapy, and third wave therapies, such as acceptance and commitment therapy and mindfulness-based cognitive behavior therapy. In a large network meta-analysis of more than 300 randomized controlled trials, it was found that all therapies have comparable effects and that there are no significant differences between therapies (Cuijpers et al., 2021). Only non-directive supportive counseling was somewhat less effective, but it is very well possible that that is caused by the fact that this therapy is often explicitly used as control condition (Cuijpers et al., 2024).

Cognitive behavior therapy is by far the best examined treatment of depression, with more than 400 randomized controlled trials examining its effects (Cuijpers et al., 2023). However, the other treatments that have been found to be effective are also examined in several dozens of studies, resulting in a strong evidence-base for several of them. One type of therapy that has been examined extensively is behavioral activation (BA).

One important characteristics of BA is that it is relatively simple compared to full CBT (Cuijpers et al., 2023). BA is based on the premise that therapists assist patients in identifying activities that are associated with improved mood and subsequently support the systematic incorporation of such positively reinforcing activities into daily life. In contrast to interventions that focus on modifying cognitive processes, BA does not require the identification and restructuring higher-level patterns of thoughts, which many patients experience as difficult and demanding to learn. Consequently, BA does not necessarily be delivered by fully trained psychotherapist or clinical psychologist. A seminal randomized controlled trial conducted in the United Kingdom demonstrated that BA delivered by nurses in primary care was not inferior to full CBT provided by highly trained therapists (Richards et al., 2016; Cuijpers et al., 2023).

BA can briefly be defined as “a psychological method aimed at increasing positive interactions between a person and the environment” (Cuijpers et al., 2020). A more extensive and precise definition would be: (Dimidjian et al., 2017): a “structured, brief psychotherapeutic approach that aims to (a) increase engagement in adaptive activities (which often are those associated with the experience of pleasure or mastery), (b)

decrease engagement in activities that maintain depression or increase risk for depression, and (c) solve problems that limit access to reward or that maintain or increase aversive control.”

Several meta-analyses have integrated the results of randomized trials examining the effects of BA in the past decade. However, all of these meta-analyses had a narrow focus, and focused only on subsets of trials examining BA for depression. For example, several meta-analyses have focused on individual BA (Stein et al., 2020; Cuijpers et al., 2023), group BA (Simmonds-Buckley et al., 2019), BA delivered by paraprofessionals and peers (Anvari et al., 2023), other have focused on digitally delivered BA (Alber et al., 2023; Huguet et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2025) or on comorbid depression and substance use disorders (Pott et al., 2022). All meta-analyses also have included a relatively small number of trials. The largest one included only 28 trials (Stein et al., 2020), while a rough estimate from our database of randomized trials of psychotherapies for depression (www.metapsy.org), suggests that at this moment there must be at least 100 trials on BA.

The goal of the current meta-analysis is to conduct a comprehensive meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials examining the effects of BA for depression. We not only included trials comparing BA in depressed adults to control conditions or other psychotherapies, but we also looked into BA in children and adolescent, in institutional settings, digital versions of BA, and trials comparing BA with pharmacotherapy or combined trials.

The best method to examine if the effects of BA differ from those of other studies, is to conduct a meta-analysis of direct comparisons. In this study, we conduct such a meta-analysis. However, BA is also often used as one component in multicomponent interventions for depression, often in combination with components such as cognitive restructuring, problem-solving, social skills training and mindfulness. In the current meta-analysis we also examined in a large sample of randomized trials on psychotherapies for depression (>500 trials), if interventions that include BA as a component are more effective than therapies that do not include BA as a component.

Methods

Identification and Selection of Studies

The current study is part of a larger meta-analytic project on psychological treatments of depression that was registered at the Open Science Framework (Cuijpers & Karyotaki, 2020; <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/825C6>). This database has been used in a series of earlier meta-analyses (Cuijpers et al., 2023), and is updated every four months. The protocol for the current meta-analysis is submitted to Zenodo before the analyses started (most of the data are already available from the main project).

Since data collection methods were similar to other papers using data from our main project (Cuijpers et al., 2023), we followed reporting guidance from the Text Recycling Research Project (Hall et al., 2025).

The studies included in the current study are identified through the larger, existing database of randomized trials on psychological treatment of depression. We searched four major bibliographical databases (PubMed, PsycINFO, Embase and the Cochrane Library; up to January 1, 2026) by combining index and free terms indicative of depression and psychological treatments, with filters for randomized controlled trials (Supplement A). All records in the database were screened by two independent researchers and all papers that could possibly meet inclusion criteria according to one of the researchers were retrieved as full-text. The decision to include or exclude a study in the database was done by the two independent researchers. Disagreements were resolved through discussion.

For the current meta-analysis, we will select (a) randomized trials in which (b) behavioral activation therapy (c) for people with depression was (c) compared to a control condition (waitlist, care-as-usual (CAU), other), to another type of therapy, pharmacotherapy or a combined treatment in (d) any age group (e) or setting (outpatient or inpatient). Depression can be defined as meeting criteria for a depressive disorder according to a diagnostic interview or as a score above the cut-off on a validated self-report depression measure.

We will distinguish four types of BA (Cuijpers et al., 2019; 2023; Mazzucchelli et al., 2009): (1) Pleasant activity scheduling (consisting of monitoring and scheduling pleasant activities, sometimes including social skills training; Lewinsohn, 1974); (2) Self-control (monitoring of activities and mood, goal setting, self-evaluation of

performance and self-administering rewards; Rehm, 1984); (3) Contextual BA (activity scheduling, self-monitoring, graded task assignment, role playing, functional analysis, mental rehearsal and mindfulness; Jacobson et al., 2001; Martell et al., 2001); and (4) Brief behavioral activation treatment for depression (contracting to change immediate environmental contingencies, goal setting and graduated task assignment, monitoring, and self-administering rewards; Lejuez et al., 2001).

We will categorize the included studies into several subsets to enable the pooling of comparable comparisons within meta-analyses. One subset comprises trials in which BA is compared with control conditions. This subset includes individually delivered BA, group-based BA, guided self-help, and mixed delivery formats, as previous research indicates that these formats yield comparable effects (Cuijpers et al., 2019). Trials directly comparing BA with other therapies will be included in a second subset. Trials of unguided self-help BA will be analyzed in a separate subset. We will also distinguish studies conducted in inpatient settings in a separate subset, given that these patients differ from outpatients and that the control conditions in inpatient care vary substantially from those typically used in outpatient settings (Cuijpers et al., 2021). Additional subsets will be constructed for studies comparing BA with pharmacotherapy, BA with combined treatment, and pharmacotherapy with combined treatment. Finally, a separate subset will be created for studies involving children and adolescents with depression, as treatment effects are generally smaller in this population (Cuijpers et al., 2020).

In order to examine if studies in which BA is a component of the intervention differ from studies in which BA is not a component, we will include all randomized trials in which any type of psychotherapy for adult depression was compared to a control condition (waitlist, care-as-usual (CAU), other). Trials on unguided self-help, inpatients, and children and adolescents will be excluded from these analyses.

Quality Assessment and Data Extraction

The methodological quality of the included studies will be evaluated using four domains of the Cochrane Collaboration's Risk of Bias (RoB) tool, version 1. This instrument examines potential sources of bias in randomized trials, including adequate generation of the allocation sequence, concealment of treatment allocation, blinding of

outcome assessors to the assigned intervention, and the handling of incomplete outcome data. The latter criterion will be considered satisfied when intention-to-treat analyses are performed, such that all randomized participants are included in the analyses. Trials will be classified as having a low risk of bias when they meet all four criteria. Study quality will be independently assessed by two researchers, and any discrepancies will be resolved through discussion.

We will also extract participant characteristics (clinical diagnosis versus a cut-off as inclusion criterion; recruitment method; mean age; proportion of women); characteristics of the psychological treatments will be coded (type of BA; type of therapy in the comparison arm (Cuijpers et al., 2020); format; number of sessions), as well as general characteristics of the studies (type of control or comparison; country).

Outcome measures

For each comparison between behavioral activation (BA) and a comparator condition, we will calculate the post-treatment effect size as the standardized mean difference (SMD; Hedges' g). Effect sizes will be obtained by subtracting the mean post-test score of the treatment group from that of the control group and dividing the difference by the pooled standard deviation. Given that several trials are expected to have relatively small sample sizes, a correction for small-sample bias will be applied. When studies do not report post-treatment means and standard deviations, change scores will be used. If these are also unavailable, binary outcomes will be converted to the SMD, or alternative reported statistics (e.g., p-values or t-statistics) will be used to derive the effect size. When means are only reported in figures, we will use Plotdigitizer 3.1.6 (<https://plotdigitizer.com/app>) to extract them. Missing standard deviations will be imputed using the pooled standard deviations of the outcome measures from other studies in the database (Furukawa et al., 2006).

In addition to calculating the SMD at post-test, we will also calculate follow-up outcomes at 6 months or longer after randomization. We will also extract study drop-out for any reason as an outcome. To further explore the association between baseline severity and outcome, we will also calculate the response rates (a 50% reduction of depressive symptoms compared to baseline) with a validated method using the baseline

means, the post-test means, the post-test SD and N (Furukawa et al., 2005). In these analyses we will conservatively assume that all dropouts are non-responders.

Meta-analyses

The meta-analyses will be conducted using the ‘metapsyTools’ package in R (version 4.1.1; Harrer et al., 2022) and RStudio (version 1.1.463 for Mac). This package was specifically developed for our meta-analytic project and imports functionality of the ‘meta’ (Balduzzi et al., 2019), ‘metafor’ (Viechtbauer, 2010), and ‘dmetar’ (Harrer et al., 2019) packages.

We will pool SMDs for each outcome domain using a random-effects model. Between-study heterogeneity variance will be estimated using the restricted maximum likelihood estimator. We will apply the Knapp-Hartung method to obtain robust confidence intervals and significance tests of the overall effect (IntHout et al., 2014). As a test of homogeneity of effect sizes, we will calculate the I^2 -statistic and its 95% CI (Higgins et al., 2003). We will also add the prediction interval (PI), which will indicate the range in which the effect size of 95% of all populations is expected to fall (Borenstein et al., 2009; 2017).

In our main analysis model, we will first aggregate the SMDs within one study (separately for each of the domains) before pooling across the studies. An intra-study correlation coefficient of $\rho=0.5$ will be assumed to aggregate effects within comparisons. We will conduct several sensitivity analyses. (1) We will estimate the pooled effect using a three-level correlated and hierarchical effects (CHE) model (Pustejovsky & Tipton, 2022). (2) We will pool SMDs while excluding outliers, using the “non-overlapping confidence intervals” approach. (3) We will pool SMDs while excluding influential cases as defined by the diagnostics in Viechtbauer and Cheung (2010). (4) We will pool SMDs when only the smallest or largest effect in each study is considered. (5) We will pool SMDs using only studies with low risk of bias. We will also use three different methods to assess and adjust for potential publication bias (Harrer et al., 2021; Maier et al., 2022): Duval and Tweedie’s trim and fill procedure (Duval and Tweedie, 2000), Rücker’s ‘Limit meta-analysis method’ (Rucker et al., 2011), and a step function selection model (McShane et al., 2016; Carter et al., 2019).

We will also conduct Egger's test of the intercept to examine asymmetry of the funnel plot (only when at least 10 studies are available).

We will conduct subgroup analyses using mixed-effects models, with between-study heterogeneity variance estimates stratified by subgroup. Subgroup analyses will only be conducted for subgroups with at least three studies per subgroup. Subgroups with fewer studies will be merged with other subgroups. We will prioritize the following subgroup analyses (depending on the number of available studies in the examined subset): type of control/comparison group, diagnosis, recruitment method, treatment format, and country. In the subset of trials comparing BA with other therapies we will also prioritize the type of therapy that is compared with BA.

Multivariable meta-regression analyses will be conducted in subsets with more than 30 comparisons, using the same study characteristics as in the subgroup analyses, as well as mean age, proportion of women, and number of sessions.

For dichotomous outcomes (the response and dropout rates) we will calculate the pooled RRs (and numbers-needed-to-treat; NNTs) and the absolute rates within each condition using the "meta" package in R. In the analyses in which we pool the outcome rates within each condition, we will synthesize the log-transformed risk ratios using a "normal-normal" random-effects model (Bakbergenuly et al., 2019). We will then use the antilog to reconvert the pooled results back to the relative risk scale. The logit-transformed response rates will also be pooled using the same approach, and final results will be reconverted using the inverse of the logit function (expit)